

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR ADAPTATION OF YOUNG TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10894628>

Abstract. *In the given article, psychological and pedagogical conditions for the professional growth of young teachers, helping to successfully enter professional activity and reduce the problems of adaptation of a young teacher are analysed.*

Keywords: *professional adaptation, young teacher, school for a young teacher.*

It is important to suggest that the vocational education system is currently undergoing major changes in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which in turn requires teachers with new pedagogical thinking, capable of becoming active subjects of innovative processes in education [1]. The teacher must have a high level of academic knowledge in the chosen specialty, general pedagogical and methodological-technological culture. The teacher must be able to communicate culturally, unobtrusively with students on the basis of subject-subject relationships, build relationships with colleagues and higher structures on the basis of friendship, cooperation, and mutual assistance.

Definitely, the concept of "adaptation" (from the Latin "adapto" - I adapt) is borrowed from biology and means adaptation to the environment. Social and professional adaptation of a teacher is the process of a teacher mastering the skills of conducting the educational process, norms and rules of behavior - interaction with colleagues, administration, students and their parents. [4]

It is not a secret that in the pedagogical literature, three components of social and professional adaptation of a teacher are traditionally distinguished: psychophysiological - the adaptation of a young teacher (all systems of his body) to unusual conditions, a lesson schedule of work and rest; socio-psychological - joining the work team through the convergence of the goals and interests of the young specialist and the group (teaching staff, students), the formation of a new psychological stereotype of behavior, the correction of personal qualities in accordance with the requirements of pedagogical activity, the acceptance of the values of organizational culture, norms and rules of behavior in educational institution; professional - the teacher's active mastery of actions (behavior) in accordance with job responsibilities, the requirements of the educational process, and the specifics of the student population; the young specialist's adaptation to new conditions, including administrative, legal, socio-economic, and management aspects.[2]

Adaptation of a teacher is the process of successfully integrating him into professional activities. The duration of the adaptation period is individual for each person, depending on the initial conditions and abilities. One of the indicators of psychological adaptation can be social well-being, which includes: - the internal state of a person: (health, mood, feelings of happiness); assessment of external conditions (perception of the situation in the country); perception of one's own position in new conditions.[3]

The psychological stress received by the teacher leads to the development of professional stress. The most important task in the psychological adaptation of a teacher is the development of resistance to factors that cause stress at work. These factors include: overload at work; the need to perform difficult to compatible functions; behavior of management, other teachers and students; poor working conditions; unfair assessment of work; inability to adapt to change. Some thinking errors, which are more or less common to almost every person, can lead to severe stress. The former student enters a new social environment and tries to find optimal forms of interaction with colleagues, students and their parents, and with the administration of the educational institution. The need to combine professional and social adaptation to a new environment is a difficult task for a young teacher. Successful adaptation in a short period of time ensures high efficiency of his further work. Difficult, protracted adaptation not only has a negative psycho-emotional impact on a person (the emergence of feelings of inferiority, uncertainty, pessimism, neuroticism and psychosomatic diseases), but also leads to a decrease in the quality of teaching and interaction with participants in the pedagogical process and, ultimately, to a deterioration in professional teacher performance indicators. Therefore, the study of adaptation processes, timely provision of real support and assistance to a young teacher becomes a very urgent task. The analysis of scientific literature, the works of domestic and foreign researchers on the problem of teacher professional development [3;4] made it possible to understand the professional development of a young teacher as a complex, continuous, nonlinear process of qualitative changes in personality, the content of which is the entry of a specialist into the professional space (the space of professional activity and professional communication), and the result is his holistic professional adaptability.

By starting teaching, a young teacher finds himself or herself in a new social and professional environment, as well as new modes of mental and physical stress, and a new sphere of relationships and interaction. In this regard, every young specialist, from the first days of entering the workforce, faces a number of interrelated tasks: to find optimal options for interaction with all participants in the educational process - students, colleagues, the administration of the educational institution, parents; skillfully apply the knowledge and practical skills acquired in a pedagogical educational institution, having previously assessed the level of use of innovative methods in the educational process and the feasibility of introducing innovations; evaluate one's own abilities, the requirements of the new social environment, professional activities and, if necessary, try to adjust one's behavior.

Consistent solution of the listed tasks is a necessary condition for favorable subsequent social and professional adaptation of a teacher starting his working life.

In the process of labor adaptation, an employee goes through the following stages:

1. The familiarization stage, at which the employee receives information about the new situation as a whole, about the criteria for evaluating various actions, and about the norms of behavior in the team.
2. Stage of adaptation or formal entry - at this stage the employee reorients, recognizing the main elements of the new value system, but for now continues to retain many of his attitudes.
3. The assimilation stage, when the employee fully adapts to the environment and identifies with the new group.
4. Identification, when the employee's personal goals are identified with the goals of the labor organization. [2]

Going through all these stages will be quick and productive if efforts are made not only by the administration of the educational institution, but also by the youngest specialist. In the process of social and professional adaptation, a young teacher has to simultaneously master several professional roles: teacher, educator, class teacher, subordinate, colleague, member of a methodological association of teachers, and everywhere it is necessary to demonstrate professional competence and skills, which, unfortunately, many lack. In this regard, the following tasks can be identified in helping novice teachers in the process of social and professional adaptation [1,2,3,4]. Studying the real professional difficulties of beginning teachers, formulating their current needs. Information and advisory support for beginning teachers in choosing advanced training programs and in building an individual educational route: creating an information bank of educational services for young specialists in the district; organization of advanced training courses; participation in creative laboratories and trainings; consulting young professionals; participation in scientific and practical conferences; involvement in experimental work; closing knowledge gaps on economic and legal issues.

By summarizing the ideas mentioned above it can be suggested that the professional development of a young teacher occurs gradually, step by step. As a result, competent, high-quality management of the process of professional adaptation and development of novice teachers helps both the professional growth of young specialists themselves and contributes to the development of a general education institution. Not a single pedagogical educational institution or pedagogical college produces fully formed, highly qualified teaching staff. It is in an educational institution that the process of becoming a teacher as a professional occurs. How the adaptation period goes and whether he finds a common language with the team determines whether the young specialist will succeed as a teacher, whether he will remain in the field of education or find himself in another field.

REFERENCES

1. Kotova, S.A. Adaptation to the position and mastering the teaching profession / S.A. Kotova // Nar. education. - 2010. - N. 8. - Pp. 121-127.
2. Redlikh, S.M. Adaptation of a young teacher / S.M. Redlich // Prof. education. Capital. - 2012. - N. 1. - Pp. 19-21.
3. Turlunova, A.V. Psychological and pedagogical support for a young teacher during the adaptation period of professional activity / A. V. Turlunova // Methodist. - 2012. - N. 7. - Pp. 20-26.
4. Shevchenko O. A. Empirical study of professional development of young teachers in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education // Concept. – 2014. – N. 07 (July). – ART 14176. – 0.5 p.l. – URL: <http://e-kon-cept.ru/2014/14176.htm>. - Mr. reg. El N. FS 77-49965. – ISSN 2304-120X.